

WHO CAN “TEST. TEST. TEST.”? THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN BOUNDARY WORK AND INSTITUTIONS IN THE ORGANIZATION OF DIAGNOSTIC TESTING FOR COVID-19

David Barbera-Tomás¹, James Bates², Enrique Meseguer¹ and Michael M. Hopkins²

¹*Ingenio (CSIC-UPV), Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain.*

²*Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU), University of Sussex Business School, Brighton, UK.*

ABSTRACT

At the start of the Covid-19 pandemic, countries were encouraged by the World Health Organization to “Test. Test. Test.” This paper compares how Spain and the UK, simultaneously facing a crisis of similar magnitude, established diagnostic testing systems that greatly differed in their organization. The paper shows how boundary work in each country, influenced by preexisting institutional conditions, defined who could provide diagnostic testing and, crucially, who was excluded during the crisis response. Results show that enduring institutional conditions allowed clinical laboratory specialists to engage in boundary work, where these specialists had access to decision makers with formal authority, with the resulting testing system reflecting their professional logic. Where this was not the case, boundary work by others, based on the logic of efficiency, was influential in the organization of testing. Our findings contribute to the understanding of the interplay between institutional conditions during a crisis, -especially conditions regulating the territorial distribution of formal authority- and boundary work. In the UK, the high centralization of authority over healthcare budgets allowed policy makers to implement a radically novel organizational solution to facilitate the scaling up of testing in newly built high-throughput labs. Conversely, in Spain devolved authority favoured local clinical laboratory specialists in their attempts to retain control of testing in their labs. Finally, the legacy of the pandemic response already appears to be very different in these two countries. In Spain, resources allocated to public hospital labs have expanded their hospitals’ testing capacity and improved their diagnostic capabilities. In the UK, the closure of newly built labs after the acute phase of the pandemic has left little infrastructural legacy from the crisis and may have limited future pandemic preparedness.

1. INTRODUCTION

The management of national responses to Covid-19 is a matter of extraordinary public interest and importance, given the magnitude of the crisis, its human and economic cost, and the potential to learn lessons in preparation for future pandemics. The case of Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) testing systems built in response to Covid-19 also offers an opportunity to analyse the creation and development of sociotechnical systems that fulfil a vital societal function to benefit public health. This paper attempts to contribute to the understanding of recent events by showing, in the contexts of Spain and the UK, how the interplay of boundary work and institutional conditions may be relevant to explaining the ability of actors to influence the organization of the testing systems. In doing so the paper also contributes to the literature

on boundary work in healthcare sociotechnical systems by addressing a call to study the interaction between boundary work and formal authority, expressed by Langley et al. (2019) and others (Chreim et al, 2013; Helfen, 2015; Vuolanto, 2015).

In early 2020, with no vaccine to counter the novel pandemic virus, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) based diagnostic tests were widely used as the first step in an effort to detect, isolate and, if necessary, treat those infected with the virus, as well as to trace their close contacts in order to break onward chains of infection (Velavan & Meyer, 2021). With this aim, the Director General of the WHO, encouraged countries to “Test. Test. Test.” to counter Covid-19 (WHO 16/3/20). National responses to Covid-19 were unprecedented in terms of the speed, scaling, and cost of diagnostic testing services, requiring rapid decisions on who would undertake all this new testing and how this huge volume of potentially life-saving activity could be organised (Tromberg *et al*, 2020).

PCR-based testing is fundamental tool for genetic analysis with many applications. It has been used since the 1980s to diagnose a range of diseases, including infections, such as AIDS and tuberculosis (Bartlett and Stirling, 2003; Venter and Richer, 2020; Gupta et al., 2020). As the Covid-19 pandemic took hold, PCR testing became the gold standard for diagnostic testing (Chaimayo et al, 2020; Tahamtan and Ardebili, 2020; Boeckmans et al, 2021). Clinical diagnosis using PCR testing requires both specific equipment and specialized human resources, generally laboratory-based. While PCR testing capacity in pre-existing clinical labs was at risk of being rapidly overwhelmed by the dimensions of the pandemic, additional resources were available in universities and commercial facilities.

This paper compares how healthcare systems in two countries, Spain and the UK, simultaneously facing a crisis of similar magnitude, developed PCR testing systems that greatly differed in their organization. We show how the interplay between boundary work and specific institutional conditions influenced which groups could provide PCR testing during the crisis response, and crucially, which groups were excluded. The notion of boundary work was initially coined to describe the discursive and practice-based attempts of researchers and polemicists to demarcate science from non-science (Gieryn, 1983). Since then, its application has expanded to many other empirical fields (Langley et al., 2019), referring generally to boundaries distinguishing actors with “decision-making authority” (Zietsma and Lawrence, 2010: 199). Boundary work is actors’ discourses and practices aimed at building, maintaining or changing the boundaries to participation in decision making in a specific field (Zietsma and

Lawrence, 2010; Langley et al., 2019; Gieryn, 1983). Literature on sociotechnical systems in healthcare, shows how attempts to exclude certain professional groups from decision-making on the implementation and use of new technologies, for example in medical imaging, have been characterised as boundary work (Burri, 2008; Barrett et al., 2012; Lindberg et al., 2017; Håland, 2011).

In Section 2 we review studies of boundary work in healthcare and highlight the need to consider its interplay with two specific conditions of the institutional context (namely institutional logics and conditions regarding formal authority) that we argue can help us to understand the fast-paced response to the health crisis that we observe. Section 3 describes the research methods used. Section 4 presents our results: In Spain and the UK, during the pandemic's acute phase, we find that the impact of different kinds of boundary work on the organization of diagnostic testing was shaped by prior institutional conditions regarding the territorial distribution of formal authority. Our findings suggest that in Spain the dominance of boundary work in line with the professional logic resulted in improved resourcing for diagnostic services run by the pre-existing clinical laboratories in hospitals. By contrast, in the UK the greater influence of boundary work in line with the logic of efficiency, by those outside the relevant clinical laboratory specialities, resulted in the expending of resources in temporary labs, decommissioned in the aftermath of the pandemic's acute phase. We conclude that proximity to formal authority appears crucial in determining the influence of boundary work in shaping the organization of testing, during a crisis. Section 5 discusses the implications of our findings and their contribution to the literature on the organization of sociotechnical systems in healthcare, while the conclusions reflect on this study's limitations, future lines of research and concerns for future pandemic preparedness.

2.CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK: BOUNDARY WORK AND INSTITUTIONAL CONDITIONS.

Our intention is to understand how, during a crisis, the discourses and practices of actors aiming to build, maintain or change the boundaries around decision making interact with specific institutional conditions. To do so, we adhere to a long tradition of institutional thinking that identifies a wide range of social phenomena within the notion of "institutions." In essence, institutions encompass both legal regulations backed by formal authority and more cognitive and normative conditions related to values, beliefs and assumptions that cannot be fully captured by analysing only formal regulations (Scott, 2001; DiMaggio and Powell, 1983;

Meyer and Rowan, 1977; Thornton, Ocasio and Lounsbury, 2015). These cognitive and normative conditions have been described in different ways: "reasoning styles" (Popp Berman, 2022), "orders of worth" (Boltanski and Thevenot, 2006) or "episteme" (Foucault, 1975), for example. Following the recent institutional turn in the literature on sociotechnical systems change (Fuenfschilling and Truffer, 2014; Strambach and Pflitsch, 2020), in this paper we apply the notion of "institutional logic" (Thornton et al., 2015; Lounsbury et al., 2021) to conceptualize the influence of values, beliefs and assumptions on actors' boundary work during a crisis. In addition, we analyse the interaction of boundary work in line with different institutional logics with the other crucial institutional condition - formal authority. These concepts, together with their contributions to the literature on sociotechnical systems in healthcare, are introduced below.

Boundary work and institutional logics

In the literature on change in socio-technical systems in healthcare, the concept of boundary work has been used to designate the discursive and practical efforts of particular groups for controlling decision-making regarding the implantation and use of new technologies, or, as Langley et al, put it, to 'claim jurisdiction over the technology and practices related to its handling' (Langley, 2019:14). Extant literature on boundary work has mainly focused on processes of innovation diffusion where the introduction of a new technology is associated with boundary work that results in structural changes to an existing socio-technical system.

The diffusion of a new technology can instigate boundary work by various actors who see 'keeping control over the machines' as important to their group (Burri, 2008:44). Actors create boundaries that distinguish between 'in-groups' and 'out-groups' (Lamont and Molnar, 2002:170) with respect to decision-making regarding the implantation and use of the new technology. Detailed studies of medical imaging technologies including X-rays, Computer Tomography, Medical Resonance Imaging or Positron Emission Tomography (Blume, 1992; Burri 2008; 2013 and Burri and Dumit, 2008) demonstrate boundary work of different types being employed in this process.

The work of Burri (2008) is of particular relevance here for several reasons. Burri studies the use of a diagnostic technology and emphasizes the competitive boundary work between different groups (radiologists and other medical specialists), who try to exclude each other from decision-making around the implantation and use of the technology. Above all, Burri identifies two forms (among others) of boundary work that can be extended to the analysis of other

medical technologies. The first relates to the professional criteria that medical specialists used to demand the installation of the new MRI equipment in the neurology, cardiology and orthopaedics departments of hospitals. These specialists argued that access to patient data was essential for interpreting the diagnosis and that the scanners should therefore be integrated into their departments, where the doctor-patient interaction was most intense. The second of these refers to radiologists' arguments for incorporating the technology into their departments, related to the efficiency in utilization gained through centralization of MRI equipment in a single location.

These two forms of boundary work are central for our analytical purpose here because they connect with widely observed institutional logics in the healthcare field. Institutional logics are coherent set of values, beliefs and assumptions that shape the 'higher organising principles' of different social fields (Thornton, Ocasio and Lounsbury, 2015; Boltanski and Thevenot, 2006). In the field of healthcare, the literature on institutional logics long identified the coexistence of the professional logic and the logic of efficiency. Historically, the dominant logic in modern socio-technical health systems, from their emergence in the mid-19th century until the 1970s, has been the professional logic (Currie and Guah, 2007; Scott et al., 2000; Raak and de Haan, 2017). As Capperallo, Tracey and Greenwood (2020:250) put it, 'the professional logic ... overarching goal is the provision of medical care deemed appropriate for the patient and delivered by qualified professionals. Essential to achieving this goal was the physician-patient relationship and the exercise of professional judgment within this relationship'.

Yet since the 1970s, at least in the developed countries (Currie and Guah, 2007), this professional logic has coexisted with what various authors have called the 'logic of efficiency'. As Andersen and Vedsted (2015:241) define it, 'in the literature, the logic of efficiency has been linked to bureaucratisation processes in healthcare systems, and various forms of managed care and formal performance monitoring. These processes ... have resulted in a range of standardized forms of care, as well as regulation of the time and skills of healthcare providers'. In sum, the literature on institutional logics in health systems has shown its usefulness for understanding the influence of both 'professional' and 'efficiency' criteria in the organization of sociotechnical systems in healthcare. Therefore, analysis of the impact of the institutional conditions on the construction of decision-making boundaries with respect to the implantation and use of medical technologies should pay attention to the influence of the professional logic and the logic of efficiency.

Boundary work and formal authority

The notions of professional logic and logic of efficiency allow us to inquire into the influence of enduring values, beliefs and assumptions when analyzing discursive or practical efforts of actors engaged in boundary work (Zietsma and Lawrence, 2010) in healthcare systems. In addition to this normative and cognitive influence, another relevant institutional condition is formal authority emanating from legal regulations (Scott, 2001; Garud et al., 2002; Rao, 2002;). As stated by Langley and coauthors in their extensive review of the literature of boundary work, on many occasions (as might be expected) ‘authorities may intervene to impose boundary relations’ (Langley et al., 2019:25). Therefore, the analysis of the institutional conditions likely to interact with actors’ boundary work in a socio-technical system should include regulatory aspects related to formal authority. So far, research on boundary work has not been able to address this interplay with formal authority in depth. Indeed, the literature has been criticized for focusing too much on discourses and practices, neglecting the relevance of the institutional conditions associated with formal authority (Chreim et al, 2013; Helfen, 2015; Vuolanto, 2015). The Langley et al. (2019:25) review includes an explicit critique acknowledging that research on boundary work has focused on ‘loosely structured settings’ and has forgotten ‘whether competitive boundary work between groups might play out differently in hierarchical settings where formal authority plays a role’.

One opportunity to explore the interplay between boundary work and institutional conditions regarding formal authority are crises. Studies of boundary work in the diffusion of medical imaging technologies, which cover years or even decades (Burri, 2008; Blume, 1992), reveal how professional associations, hospital departments or companies employ discursive strategies and practices to secure the control of the new technologies. However, during a crisis, these practices might be expected to be of more limited influence while formal authority moves to the fore as the urgency of intervening must obviate lengthy negotiations between actors seeking control over new technologies typical of boundary work processes (Quarantelli, 1988; Whittaker, McLennan and Handmer, 2015).

The Covid-19 pandemic offers an opportunity to delve into the interplay of boundary work and institutional contexts, thereby contributing to an area of literature currently identified as underdeveloped. The focal technology in the present paper, PCR testing, was well established prior to the pandemic, rather than new (e.g. see Hopkins, 2006). Yet, the sudden onset of a crisis affecting established sociotechnical systems for diagnostic testing posed many challenges

similar to those that arise in the diffusion of a new technology. Many aspects of laboratory organization, such as the physical space to house an influx of new machines and staff, the composition of human resources needed, and the logistics for testing samples and laboratory consumables, were suddenly brought into question by the urgent need to scale-up testing. In this context, our research question asks how the interplay between boundary work and institutional conditions shapes the organization of diagnostic testing during a health crisis?

3. METHODS

Case selection

This article originates from a research programme focused on exploring the organization of diagnostic testing in a range of countries during the first two years of the Covid-19 pandemic. During the period June 2020-May 2022, the programme's international team of researchers met weekly (with few breaks) to discuss diagnostic testing in 6-8 countries under a common framework that facilitated the gathering and analysis of data to address a number of topics related to diagnostic testing. During the course of the research, it was observed that the UK testing system was, in organizational terms, an outlier in the degree to which testing capacity was centralized (see Moon et al. 2020). In particular, the UK system differed from Spain, which otherwise had similarities with the UK. These two relatively wealthy European countries, with populations of around 67 million and 47 million retrospectively, have comprehensive publicly funded healthcare systems that were both severely impacted by rising case numbers in the early months of the Covid-19 pandemic. Both had to respond with a very rapid scale-up of their diagnostic testing provision - in contrast to other countries studied (e.g. Germany, South Korea) where existing systems were more adequate, at least initially (see Figure 1 and 2). The UK's highly centralized scale-up involved building large and entirely new labs, while in Spain prior regional structures for infectious disease testing were maintained.

Data sources

The research reported in this article is informed by documents collated contemporaneously as events unfolded (including from newspapers/ websites, stakeholder policy statements and reports as well as academic publications), together with key informant interviews with a range of stakeholders active in the shaping of diagnostic testing services. Primary and secondary sources have been synergistically influential in the selection of sources. Relevant stakeholders for interview have often been identified from documentary sources, and interviewees have

helped to identify other key figures, often out of the public eye. Moreover, interviewees have referred the authors to documents disclosing relevant contextual information. Documents have the advantage of being able to provide researchers with precise details while interviews have been essential in revealing the sensitive struggles between stakeholder groups and provide explanations for the shaping of systems that may not be published.

Interviews were undertaken in two phases, in late 2020 and mid-2022, coinciding with the height of diagnostic testing to reduce community transmission of Covid-19, and the reduction of this activity. In total we conducted 51 interviews with a duration of $\frac{3}{4}$ to $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours (26 in the UK and 25 in Spain), following the same protocol based around a semi-structured questionnaire (with research ethics approval, from the University of Sussex and from Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas). Of these, 23 interviews from Spain and 21 from the UK were recorded and transcribed. In some cases it was not possible to record the interviews due to interviewees' sensitivities, and data from unrecorded interviews has not been used in this paper. Interviews were undertaken on condition of strict anonymity, requiring some minor edits to redact quotes used in the paper. Spanish interviewees were interviewed in Spanish, with translation of quoted material provided by the Spanish co-authors.

[INSERT TABLE 1 AND TABLE 2 ABOUT HERE]

The types of stakeholder interviewed in each country are indicated in Table 1 and Table 2. The titles of some stakeholder groups differ between the two countries, but the same range of functions related to testing are covered in both. The labels used reflect the case narrative, as well as different national specialisations – for example, in Spain the leading professionals belong to the specialization of microbiology, while in the UK a sub-profession of clinical virology exists in addition to microbiology.

The organization of the Spanish healthcare system is completely devolved to 17 autonomous regions. This research has analysed the creation and evolution of testing services in four of these regions, representing approximately one-third of the total population. Spanish interviewees expressed their perspectives on both the national system as a whole and the specific region in which they work. In the text, we have tried to differentiate between evidence specific to the regions studied and generalizations about the national system as a whole.

Interviews for the UK include perspectives from three out of four nations of the UK. Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland have healthcare systems that are generally autonomous from England, however during the pandemic a unified laboratory network was created, which is the central object of study in the UK case.

Data analysis

Transcribed interview data was read line-by-line to identify key themes relevant to the re-organization of the testing system. This has allowed for the identification of gaps in the data, which were then addressed by seeking additional sources as needed. To answer our research question, we focus our data analysis on discourses and practices (Langley et al., 2019) related to the exclusion of other actors from decision-making around the implementation and use of PCR testing technology and in the most relevant institutional conditions interacting with boundary work. We abductively iterated between data and theory to identify the forms of boundary work most influential in the organization of the Covid-19 testing system in each country. As Timmermans and Tavory, (2012:180) recommended, we have allowed our results to emerge from “abductive analysis through the iterative dialogue (both metaphorical and literal) between data and an amalgam of existing and new conceptualizations”. For example, during the analysis of the Spanish case, we noted the remarkable effort of medical professionals and associations to draw discursive boundaries about who should (and should not) be in charge of the PCR testing system, based on the criterion of professional competence. Inspired by studies of boundary work in medical imaging, (Burri and Dumit, 2008, Burri 2008, 2013) and institutional logics in health care (Caperallo et al., 2007; Currie and Guah, 2007; Scott et al., 2000; Raak and de Haan, 2017), we conceptualized these efforts as boundary work in line with the professional logic. Additionally, in the case of the UK we find further influential boundary work that emphasizes the need to standardize and centralize Covid-19 testing. These observations again direct us back to Burri's work and institutional logics, and so we label these efforts as boundary work in line with the logic of efficiency. Furthermore, we observed that the proximity to formal authority of actors' engaging in boundary work had been crucial in explaining the influence of professional logic or the logic of efficiency in decision-making. When iterating with the literature on boundary work (especially in the extensive review by Langley et al., 2019), we identify this is a gap in the literature.

We use narrative synthesis to present our results for the two countries (cases). Narrative synthesis can be particularly valuable as it provides a way to capture and convey the richness

and complexity of new and unexpected findings (Pope and Mays, 1996; Riessman, 2008; Goden-Biddle and Locke, 2006). These narrative syntheses make it possible to identify key themes that run through the collected evidence in the two cases, which we attempt to compare systematically. Thus, we will first present the most relevant conditions of the institutional context of infectious disease diagnosis in the healthcare systems of the two countries before the pandemic. We then show the most influential forms of boundary work in each country and the interplay between boundary work and formal authority. Finally, we conclude our narrative by showing the impact of this interplay between boundary work and formal authority on health systems after the acute phase of the pandemic. To ensure verification of claims made by sources, wherever possible we have used multiple perspectives from each stakeholder group and there has been triangulation of findings between different interviewees and/or documents - including the use of historical sources detailing key contextual factors prior to the pandemic.

[INSERT FIGURE 1 and FIGURE 2 ABOUT HERE]

4. FINDINGS

4.1 The institutional conditions in Spain and UK

The Spanish institutional conditions for the diagnosis of infectious diseases

Following a reform in 2002, the organization of Spain's healthcare system is fully devolved to 17 regions (autonomous communities). Correspondingly, the central government's health ministry is relatively small compared to other ministries (Sabando et al., 2020). At interview, a Spanish public health expert describes the situation as follows:

“(The ministry) is simply useless, it was emptied of everything [after the 2002 reform], it has few civil servants left. It has little budget compared to other ministries ... Politicians in Madrid see it as a second-rate ministry with very little money.” (Public health expert)

As a consequence of the 2002 reform, microbiology laboratories in public hospitals are under the authority of the regional governments. During the Covid-19 pandemic response it was these hospital labs that scaled-up their testing capacity to cope with the crisis, based on existing PCR technology used for molecular diagnosis of infectious diseases since the 1990s (Pérez-Trallero, 2003).

Most major Spanish hospitals established clinical microbiology labs independently of other hospital labs such as haematology in the 1960s and 1970s (Perez and Álvarez, 2010). In Spain, as in other countries, there has been a strong trend towards centralization and automation in recent decades that threatens the organizational form of the independent hospital microbiology laboratory in many contexts (Pérez-Saenz, 2012). Some regions implemented a centralized lab model for their populations, resulting in the closure of a number of hospital microbiology labs. In centralized hospital labs, microbiological tests became services offered alongside those of other specialties. The penetration of lab centralization trends varies by region (Salvadó, 2012).

Clinical microbiologists are responsible for the running of hospital microbiology labs. The professional specialty of Microbiology and Parasitology has been institutionalized in the educational and training system since the 1970s (Pérez and Álvarez, 2010). Clinical microbiologists have long emphasized the need for testing in proximity to the patient for the correct diagnosis of infectious diseases. Clinical microbiologists are responsible not only for performing the tests in the labs but also for interpreting the results. For this reason, they argue, their activity also requires proximity to other hospital specialists in charge of the treatment of patients (Bermejo and García, 2010).

In 1981 the SEIMC (Spanish Society of Infectious Diseases and Clinical Microbiology), the association that groups these medical professionals, was created. Prominent members of this society have participated in the different governmental commissions that have structured the specialty of microbiology since then (Perez and Álvarez, 2010). Several sources confirm the role of SEIMC in constituting the national community of clinical microbiology professionals (García et al., 2008; Ausina, 2003; Pérez and Álvarez, 2010). The SEIMC has, on occasion problematized the trend towards laboratory centralization. For example, the first edition (2006) of the "SEIMC Treatise on Infectious Diseases and Clinical Microbiology", aimed at the training of professionals, explains tension between what they see as good clinical practice and organizational efforts focused on efficiency:

'Currently, and in the name of resource optimization, there is a tendency to concentrate more and more diagnostic units ... This analytical neoconception of clinical laboratories is hardly compatible with the functional conception of true clinical microbiology, in which the patient's clinical data are as important an instrument as the clinical sample for the etiological diagnosis of infectious diseases' (Matas et al., 2006: 53-54).

This discursive struggle has been maintained over the years. In 2019, a SEIMC document with recommendations for diagnostic testing mentioned that:

'there is a centralizing tendency of laboratories that results in the creation of 'mega-organizations' However, in the case of Microbiology, this centralization leads to a distancing of the patient from the diagnostic services.' (SEIMC, 2019:5)

The existence of an active professional association in Spain does not in itself preclude the advance of organizational initiatives predicated on efficiency. Yet, as we will see in the next section, the influence of the professional body's stance can be seen in the boundary work that shaped the expanding PCR testing system during the Covid-19 response.

The UK institutional conditions for the diagnosis of infectious diseases.

The UK's comprehensive healthcare system is funded through taxation, governed by the devolved administrations of the four home nations, and delivered through distinct entities: NHS England, NHS Scotland, NHS Wales, and HSC Northern Ireland. Although UK annual healthcare funding has steadily increased in real terms, growth slowed after the 2008 financial crisis. As a result, healthcare systems in the UK have been under financial strain in recent years (NHS Confederation, 2017), with negative consequences for the systems' responses to Covid-19.

In particular, England's network of public health laboratories was rationalized following public health reforms between 2003-2012, that left Public Health England (PHE), an agency outside of the NHS with responsibility for pandemic response (amongst other public health priorities), largely reliant on testing capacity in NHS labs with a combined NHS/PHE role. NHS pathology labs were also identified as a target for efficiency savings by the Government's Department of Health - subsequently the Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC) - as expressed by the Chief Medical Officer (CMO):

'the Pathology Modernisation Programme [...] is encouraging rationalisation of NHS pathology services. The reasons for this change of emphasis are better use of scarce human resources [...] efficient use of expensive sophisticated equipment, introduction of new technologies and the development of information technology.' (Chapter 5, Department of Health 2002)

Reports by Lord Carter between 2006 and 2016, subsequently identified budget savings of £250-500 million per year through a process of consolidation and centralization of pathology labs to increase the cost-efficacy of services (Carter, 2008). Some hospital labs were closed in favour of centralized labs in 'hub and spoke' networks of labs, in a process of reorganization that was still ongoing immediately before the pandemic (NHS England, 2019).

In sum, the NHS pathology labs have been subjected to rationalization over recent decades as part of a well-established efficiency drive, enacted through central government policies. One online news organization, editorialized on the logic of these reforms in 2011:

'The cuts to hospital budgets are finally pushing many [hospital] trusts to make long overdue improvements such establishing [sic] one high quality pathology service supporting several hospitals, rather than persevering with their own, inadequate, cottage industry.' (Vise, 2011).

The analogy to a ‘cottage industry’ recalls pre-industrial small batch production, largely replaced by the rise of factories, suggesting the historical configuration of NHS labs was no longer efficient.

The focus on efficiency in recent years has had its correlate in the reduced influence of specialist medical professionals, notably including reductions in specialist clinical virologist positions, as interview quotes from two virologists illustrate:

“The government never, never agreed to increase the consultant virology numbers [...] We had something like 80 plus consultant virologists just about 20, 30 years ago, we are now 43 full time equivalents” (Lighthouse Lab advisor 1).

“So within virology within the NHS, the numbers of [highly-trained] staff [...] has been progressively reduced. And the funding to train new clinical scientists has been demolished in effect. You’ve had this slow attrition of the science of clinical virology for 20 years and we’ve seen the consequences of that now.” (Lighthouse Lab advisor 2)

This undermining of the specialist professions in pathology has also manifested in the weakened influence of professional associations (each clinical discipline is represented by a Royal College and possibly other associations as well, such as the UK Clinical Virology Network). For example, during the planning of the new centralized networks of labs in 2016, the Royal College of Pathologists suggested they were not included in the consultation on the design of the new pathology quality assurance dashboard (Royal College of Pathologists, 2016). While this particular concern was subsequently addressed by NHS England (2019, p12), it reflects the marginalized position of professional organizations in the face of centralized efforts to seek efficiency. The following (recent) critique from Clinical Virologists further illustrates consequences of their low influence:

‘Pathology centralisation, often at sites remote from acute services, particularly impacts smaller disciplines such as virology, and may discourage trainees who value patient contact, clinical interaction, and research. The medical establishment needs to be reminded that 70-80% of diagnoses in the NHS are made as a result of pathology investigations. It is therefore surprising that other Royal Colleges allowed the cost saving exercise resulting from the Carter Report to have gained favour’ (Banatvala et al. 2022).

4.2 PCR testing for Covid-19 in Spain

In this subsection we will show how boundary work in line with the professional logic was influential in the scale-up of PCR testing in Spain. When Covid-19 emerged, Spain's central Ministry of Health had limited capacity, due to prior reform. The most relevant crisis intervention of the central government was to promote the development of scientific and technical guidance on Covid-19 testing, ultimately undertaken by the Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII), a public institution devoted to promoting research in biomedicine and health sciences, itself part of the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities. In January 2020, when Spain's first Covid-19 cases emerged, ISCIII's microbiology research lab in Madrid was the only officially designated laboratory that could perform PCR-based diagnostic testing. As cases increased, clinical microbiologists in regional hospitals labs began to perform Covid-19 testing. These were the ones who implemented the protocols for Covid-19 testing and faced the technical and logistical challenges associated with scaling up testing capacity. The head of a hospital lab commented on the role of the microbiology profession, and their labs, during the first weeks of the pandemic:

"the initiative at that time came from the microbiology laboratories themselves, there was nothing regulated in that sense ... we microbiologists have been ahead of the problem" (Head of hospital lab 2)

As the crisis grew, in addition to testing Covid-19 patients in hospitals, these labs were also charged with community testing – i.e., tests performed on suspected Covid-19 cases, beyond the hospital context. Individuals were swabbed in primary care or at “drive in” centres and their samples were sent to hospitals for testing by microbiologists who also could access the patients' personal clinical data. This great increase in testing volumes required extra resources.

Therefore, a further intervention by ISCIII involved a national-level role in overseeing the accreditation of labs based in universities and research institutes, allowing these to join efforts to increase PCR testing capacity across the country. These labs, previously outside of the healthcare system, had the technical capabilities to perform PCR testing, developed from experience in non-clinical areas such as research or veterinary testing. By 14th April 2020, 13 of these ‘external labs’ were already accredited by ISCIII, rising to a total of 85 in July 2022. However, regional governments held the authority to integrate newly accredited labs into the publicly funded testing system.

The SEIMC reacted to the accreditation of external labs through two public statements. According to interviewees, the first SEIMC statement had an aggressive tone against the external labs accredited by ISCIII and was rapidly retracted. The second statement reflected the established professional argument of the need for testing in proximity to the patient (SEIMC, 2020): *'clinical microbiologists not only do PCR, but also provide information and support for the diagnosis and follow-up of patients'*. From this perspective, only hospital labs, which had close contact with the clinical context of the patient, not available to external labs, were legitimized to perform Covid-19 testing.

The statement contained further examples of organizational practices that made it “difficult” according to SEIMC, to incorporate external labs, including *'sample distribution, preparation and inactivation [of the virus present in samples], sample traceability and validation, data protection, as well as personnel biosafety'*. The text of SEIMC's second statement was made public on 14th April 2020, at the height of Spain's first wave of Covid-19 cases, following validation of the first four external labs, and the same day that ISCIII approved a further 9 external labs. The statement considered the possibility that external labs could contribute to testing Covid-19 in the future, but suggested any potential contribution should be organized under the supervision of the established hospital microbiology labs:

'it is absolutely essential, unavoidable and necessary ... that each of the (external) research centres that decide to collaborate in this task be under the coordination of an experienced Hospital Microbiology Service' (SEIMC 2nd statement 14/04/2020)

The SEIMC statement also declared that the operation of external labs should not jeopardize the supply of key resources for hospital labs, such as DNA extraction reagents, one of the resources that experienced the most stock-outs during those months:

'In no case can the implementation of these support laboratories can jeopardize the normal development of diagnostics in clinical laboratories due to possible competition in the supply of reagents necessary for the development of tests.'

At interview, the heads of external labs contributing to Covid-19 testing capacity referred to the SEIMC statements - especially to the first, retracted, statement- as proof of the hostility of the clinical microbiology community to new initiatives trying to extend the Spanish testing system's boundaries. However, clinical microbiologists generally echoed SEIMC's concerns at interview:

“Throughout the pandemic, ISCIII has [been] dedicated to validating various things that were not... that it is not its mission to validate them, such as validating laboratories ... it is not ISCIII mission in any case” (Head of hospital lab 3)

“(The ISCIII) accredited laboratories that were not possibly prepared to do PCR on a massive scale It even pissed off many microbiologists” (Head of hospital lab 2).

“this action (of ISCIII) has been quite controversial among clinical microbiologists, but not among all clinical microbiologists ... I can understand it in the sense that ... there were centres that were not very accreditable” (Head of external lab 3).

Given the resistance of clinical microbiologists to testing at external labs it is notable that the perception of all Spanish interviewees undertaken in 2022 was that the overall contribution of external labs to Covid-19 testing in Spain had been low. The fact that there is no official compilation of data may also indicate the low perceived relevance of external labs in the Covid-19 testing system. The Ministry of Health reports 58,319,203 PCR tests were undertaken as part of the publicly-funded response from the start of the pandemic until April 2022, when the ending of the acute phase of the pandemic in Spain was marked by a change in testing strategy (data from the Ministry of Health)¹. It is difficult to know the contribution of the external labs to this total, as it is not explicitly published. According to email correspondence with around a quarter of those external labs, we estimate that perhaps only ~1% of Covid-19 PCR testing was actually undertaken by ISCIII accredited external labs (see Annex 1 for further details).

Several microbiologists and policy makers were of the opinion that the contribution of external laboratories had been scarce because it was simply not necessary. Some of the heads of external labs highlighted how they had contributed to the Covid-19 test system by providing capacity to test in specific situations such as testing of nursing homes residents or assisting hospitals in cases of technical failures. It is not our aim to pass judgment on the technical merits of these labs in the Spanish testing system, but rather to examine the interplay of boundary work and institutional conditions concerning formal authority and their role in shaping testing provision, which we explore in the next subsection.

¹ Available at:

<https://www.sanidad.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/ccayes/alertasActual/nCov/pruebasRealizadas.htm>

Boundary work and formal authority

We argue that, in Spain, professionals' boundary work was effective in excluding external labs because it was backed by prior institutional conditions structuring the territorial distribution of formal authority. The central government's health ministry did not have the capacity to act even though during the acute phase of the pandemic it had been granted with exceptional powers.

"It is a matter of institutional culture ... the problem is that the ministry does not want to do anything ... The remnants of health national centres come from another era [prior the last reform of 2002 that returned competencies to the regions] ... one of the things why many economies of scale are not taken advantage of at the country level is because the ministry neglects all this ... the few centralized centres that are left are remnants after the wreck [of 2002]." (Public health expert)

Under these conditions, the responsibility to set up the boundaries of the decision-making about the organization of the testing system rested primarily with the regional authorities. This is illustrated by the case of the external laboratory most prominent in the media, the laboratory of the veterinary faculty of the Complutense University of Madrid ('UCM'). During March 2020, UCM researchers created a network of university labs to provide testing services for nursing homes, which was active at the height of the first wave of cases. This testing activity was considered as a successful case by prominent representatives of the scientific community, such as Margarita del Val, from the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). In a published interview, del Val regretted what they reported as the exclusion of external labs from testing and referred to UCM as an example of the potential contribution external labs could make:

"It could have been done in many places and it has not been done. Frustrated, yes, and angry, too. Especially seeing what has happened in the residences [nursing homes] in Madrid, where in many of them no tests were carried out. Those that did test isolated the positives, prevented contagion and avoided mortality. The key was to diagnose and we have been offering it and it has not been accepted. A group at the Complutense ... has been testing in residences. Seeing how well they worked, they should have left many more to us" (Sevillano, 2020b).

Despite this notoriety, the UCM network ceased testing after June 2020, when the collaboration agreement with the Madrid regional authorities expired. UCM network leaders expressed their willingness to continue their contribution to the testing system in future waves in a letter to the president of the Community of Madrid (one of Spain's 17 regional authorities), which was apparently not answered (Villareal, 2020).

The case of UCM illustrates the role of formal authority in setting the boundaries of decision-making around the organization of the sociotechnical system for Covid-19 testing. At interview, the heads of other external labs active in PCR testing also felt that they received little support from regional authorities, and attributed this lack of support to the influence of medical professionals:

"our contact with the regional authorities was complex, and it was slow, and it was... at some moments, I got the impression that they wanted us to fail... there were professional issues behind there... that influenced the regional authorities so that somehow we were left without supply" (Head of external lab 1)

"my impression is that ... it is the healthcare network itself, which decides what to do and what not to do, and imposes it on the regional authorities" (Head of external lab 2)

"There has been an absolute reluctance of the, of the systems of analysis eh... let's say conventional, in the health system ...They did not see with good eyes, neither that we had the capacity nor that we could give the adequate guarantee of quality ... [and that has been caused] possibly by other type of problems related to competences, between collectives, official colleges and others" (Head of external lab 4).

Indeed, some clinical microbiologists confirmed their influence on the local authorities in the regions studied, with leading microbiologists even noted as participating in committees set up by regional authorities to deal with the crisis.

"I have to say that a lot of attention has been paid in this region, a lot of attention has been paid to microbiologists" (Head of hospital lab 1).

"I have a lot of attention here by regional authorities and I have been helping them as far as I can constantly" (Head of hospital lab 2).

It is important to note that the inclusion of experts into these regional committees does not seem to have been the result of an institutionalization of scientific advice prior to the pandemic but of ‘the need to anchor the measures taken in the public's confidence in science’, as a recent report put it (Valcárcel et al., 2023:208).

Although the external labs were supported by other national level institutions such as ISCIII, they did not have access to the regional authorities – who were the actors with the most formal power in the PCR testing system. In contrast, the clinical microbiologists responsible for hospital labs had the backing of these authorities - at least in the regions we studied. As the quotes from the heads of external labs state (above), it is likely that the boundary work of microbiologists, in line with the professional logic, was decisive in the exclusion of external laboratories from testing by regional governments. The case thus illustrates the importance of territorial institutional conditions regarding formal authority in decision-making that set the context for this boundary work to occur at the regional level during the crisis.

The impact of boundary work after the pandemic acute phase

Both the human resources (such as laboratory technicians) and the technological resources that regional authorities injected into the PCR testing system remained mainly within the boundaries of the clinical microbiology labs. Lab directors confirmed at interview that a part of the new resources from the pandemic would be kept indefinitely in hospital labs. These clinical microbiologists state that, thanks to these resources, the infectious disease diagnostic services provided by clinical microbiology labs have improved considerably, improving preparedness for future pandemics:

“in many places they (microbiologists) have implemented, in addition to ... practices for Covid, a whole series of actions that produce a lot of benefits for hospitalized patients ... This is something that should not disappear, and that will also be very important to address ... possible new pandemics.” (Head of hospital lab 5)

“all these techniques that we are going to implement, that are being implemented in microbiology, all this technological revolution that is going on, we can diagnose eh... many infections in... in hours. In the first hour.” (Head of hospital lab 6)

“By having (more) laboratory technicians, the activity that can be carried out ... is totally different and the activity that can be carried out is much more intense” (Head of hospital lab 1)

SEIMC has also been strengthened by the pandemic. Its 2022 annual meeting recorded 11% higher attendance than at the last congress in 2019, and its latest budgets show, according to the association's president, 'a significant surplus compared to previous years, mainly justified by greater collaboration and commitment on the part of the pharmaceutical industries and those dedicated to microbiological diagnosis' (Rivero, 2022). One microbiologist, who plays an active role in SEIMC, comments on the growth of the association:

"A total increase in coordination and many more uh... (professionals) affiliated... to the scientific society. Much more visibility of the society, for the better" (Head of hospital lab 3).

At interview, microbiologists mention that the overall "visibility" of the profession and of infectious disease diagnosis has also improved considerably because of their role in the pandemic. Other interviewees corroborate this position. A policy-maker and a high-level official with considerable decision-making power on health policies in their regions praise the work of microbiology labs and also of SEIMC, which was very active in the production and dissemination of clinical guidelines and recommendations during the pandemic:

"microbiology laboratories ... have acquired a lot of importance, because of the pandemic, because microbiologists have really acquired an important role ... they have been able to be up to date, catch up, and help, and add, that is, I think they have done very well" (Policymaker 1).

"I think that the SEIMC has been one of the societies that has made the best positions explaining when to do analysis, when not to do it, what they are for ... to the rest of the health system, and also to the population ... Their positions have been very measured, and I sincerely like it the most ... much better than other associations of medical professionals" (Policymaker 2).

In summary, the Spanish clinical microbiologists' professional stance, apparent before the pandemic – and articulated by SEIMC – appears to have been influential in shaping the organizational structure of the PCR testing system during the Covid-19 crisis, ensuring through boundary work its influence of formal decision-making at the regional level to maintain PCR testing centred for Covid-19 in hospital-based labs. The resources that flowed to these labs to deal with the crisis have allowed them to grow and improve their services in the aftermath of acute phase of the pandemic. The devolved nature of the territorial institutional conditions shaping the healthcare system in Spain precluded much influence from formal authority beyond the regional authorities, for example from the central government's Ministry of Health. This is an important point of comparison with the UK case that follows in the next section.

4.3 PCR testing for Covid-19 in the UK

During the scale-up of PCR testing in the UK, boundary work by non-specialists dominated over that of the professional clinical virologists. In particular, boundary work focused on the opportunity to gain greater efficiency through centralization, standardization and streamlined logistics during the rapid scaling of PCR test capacity, with this emphasis taking precedence over professional concerns, such as maintaining linkage to wider clinical data during the interpretation of test results.

When the Covid-19 threat was first discussed by the UK Government's Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE), it was considered that the UK had a 'good centralized diagnostic capacity' (SAGE, 22/01/20; p.2), referring to the UK's national reference laboratory for novel respiratory infections in PHE Colindale (London), which had rapidly developed an in-house PCR-based test for SARS-CoV-2 (PHE, 2020).

However, PHE's labs did not scale-up test capacity as quickly as wider NHS labs and policy makers had expected (Clark, Cookson & Hughes, 2020). A policymaker outlined PHE's inability to scale-up testing as hoped:

"[anonymized] kept on asking Public Health England, like their plans to scale [...] And [anonymized] just saw it, this is like, this is not going to work. We need to set up something different." (Policymaker 2)

Following this recognition in mid-March 2020, an ambitious vision was developed by a small group of senior government advisors. This aimed to rapidly scale-up PCR capacity for community testing for the UK population, without reliance on PHE and NHS hospital labs. This group outlined a strategy to build new large-scale labs, so-called Lighthouse Labs, thereby allowing pre-existing clinical labs to focus on testing hospital patients and staff. The strategy involved discursive boundary work to justify the exclusion of NHS and PHE. A policymaker involved in the implementation of this strategy described the Government's evaluation (in March 2020) of the PCR testing performed by NHS and PHE, and its shortcomings:

"In early March [...] PHE and the NHS [were] just using their own labs, which were just a cottage industry of nine-to-five staff with their own, you know PCR machines, but they weren't like industrial PCR machines. They were [...] mixing their own reagents, and it wasn't, it wasn't an industrial operation, but it was never meant to be." (Policymaker 2)

Another policymaker also emphasized issues in line with the efficiency logic, such as standardization of testing and management, logistics, costs and supply chains, which excluded the established NHS and PHE labs from community testing.

“Relying on the fact that somebody's running a test [in NHS and PHE] that you haven't seen, that you haven't got quality standards for, a supply chain that you do not know the quality or robustness of in locations where the logistics is not clear [...] [scaling-up in NHS and PHE labs required] retooling of potentially hundreds of small organizations, each with their own standards, management, ways of working, etcetera, etcetera, but let alone the concept of invoicing and who was paying for all of this [...] it is simpler, faster and you know ultimately more robust to establish centres de novo than try and change the working practices, standards, supply chains and management of a wide range of other things.” (Policymaker 4)

It is notable that this boundary work continued the pre-pandemic narrative that highlighted heterogeneity and poor scalability of the “cottage industry” constituted by NHS and PHE labs.

Virology experts that could provide a specialist professional perspective in decision-making were excluded at the point at which the Lighthouse Labs were envisioned. Evidence from interviews and from documents submitted to Parliament by the UK Clinical Virology Network (UK CVN, 2020) argue that virologists were not consulted in the decision-making process concerning the creation of the Lighthouse Labs to perform PCR community testing for Covid-19. A clinical virologist involved in the implementation of the government's strategy commented on this:

“For some reason the government and the advisory bodies [...] they wanted to engage not with the clinical virologists who have the virology experience, and run the labs [...] That was a really strange decision and I don't think anybody could understand that [...] it did seem to be a weakness and I know a lot of virologists felt cut out of the loop [...] The virologists as a network felt they weren't being involved in strategy decisions, testing decisions, interpretation.” (Lighthouse Lab advisor 4)

The lack of influence of senior clinical lab professionals in decision-making around community PCR testing contrasts with the Spanish case. Furthermore, the exclusion of professional expertise in clinical virology from decision-making happened also at other levels of the system. It was reflected in the leadership of ‘NHS Test and Trace’ (the organization established to oversee Covid-19 testing, who had industry experience in retail and telecommunications rather than medicine), while the building of the Lighthouse Lab network was led by individuals with

expertise in drug discovery and automation – necessary for achieving higher-throughput testing (Iacobucci, 2020). Reflective commentary by clinical virologists in the British Medical Journal succinctly summarises the extent of the boundary work by non-specialists:

‘the Test and Trace system, which delivered widespread community testing, was established in isolation from NHS and Public Health England clinical virology services, and headed by a person with little experience in healthcare.’ (Banatvala et al. 2022)

The UK Government’s diagnostic testing strategy, was published in April 2020 (DHSC, 2020a), and outlines different roles for pre-existing clinical labs and new labs as distinct ‘pillars’ of UK testing provision. Figure 1 compares the Covid-19 PCR testing capacity of pre-existing clinical labs (part of Pillar 1) with the capacity of the network of new Lighthouse Labs created during the pandemic (part of Pillar 2). Remarkably, in a break from pre-pandemic healthcare administration, the Lighthouse Labs were established as a unified network that spanned all four of the UK’s home nations, while being controlled and funded centrally by the DHSC (DHSC, 2020b).

The Lighthouse Labs were created in newly fitted-out spaces, rather than pre-existing clinical testing facilities with accreditation and full integration with NHS IT systems. Table 3 lists each of the UK’s Lighthouse Labs, together with the commercial and not-for-profit organizations that were contracted centrally by DHSC to deliver testing capacity, as initially proposed in the April 2020 strategy (DHSC, 2020a). The resulting new capacity was very rapidly available and highly scalable. The Lighthouse Labs began testing toward the end of March 2020, when provision by the pre-existing NHS labs (Pillar 1) had reached 18,000 tests per day. While the NHS labs more than doubled their capacity by the end of April, the Lighthouse Labs had more than exceeded NHS capacity within one month of starting up. Figure 3 shows that the majority of PCR test capacity until May 2022 continued to be provided by Pillar 2, including the Lighthouse Labs.

[INSERT FIGURE 3 ABOUT HERE]

[INSERT TABLE 3 ABOUT HERE]

Table 3 shows that during 2020 most Lighthouse Labs were established through DHSC contracts with commercial and not-for-profit organizations rather than hospitals, but this situation reversed in 2021 as more hospitals were awarded contracts. Lighthouse Lab operators were expected to deliver daily test volumes in the tens of thousands. This was achieved by recruiting hundreds of staff at each site, and implementing a standardised approach to testing using the same protocol as other Lighthouse Labs - enabling shared logistics and the flexible allocation of workload across the Lighthouse network.

The inclusion of new privately operated testing providers in the Lighthouse Lab network, and apparent reduced role for the NHS, attracted much critical media attention. This included concerns over lower quality testing practices due to lack of professional supervision as well as an initial lack of formal accreditation in the newly formed labs (IBMS 2021; Sample, 2021). Further criticism targeted the Milton Keynes Lighthouse Laboratory, where sub-standard practices in the handling of viral material by staff was investigated and broadcast in a documentary by BBC Panorama (BBC, 2021). One newly established commercial Lighthouse Lab in Wolverhampton provided approximately 43,000 incorrect test results to individuals in England and Wales, resulting in its closure (Pym, 2021).

Lighthouse Labs' services differed from standard NHS lab testing in that the samples arriving for testing did not have the patient's clinical information linked to them. This was a deliberate decision to improve the speed of response, as one policymaker explained:

“The differences were that we [the Lighthouse Laboratories] had no patient information, so all that information governance around patient information was not necessary because we had none. Deliberately.” (Policymaker 4)

This diagnostic practice is remarkably different from the professional emphasis linking patient data to testing to aid interpretation of test results. In the Spanish case, this prerogative of professionals to access clinical data was used in boundary work by hospital microbiologists to exclude external labs that did not have access to patient data from testing. A UK clinical virologist suggested that the omission of personal (clinical) data is suboptimal compared with usual diagnostic practices in NHS clinical virology labs:

“What we want to do is make sure that that result is right for that patient, and there's a much more sort of embedded service around that result. You know we don't just send them out [...] we prefer to have, a proper pathway for that patient to be managed appropriately, and

unfortunately, because of the numbers of samples that were coming through, we ended up treating it more like a screening test rather than a diagnostic [test].” (Clinical Virologist 3)

The absence of clinical data in the testing process was reflected in the internal organization of the Lighthouse Labs which, compared to the NHS and PHE labs, had less direct involvement of clinical virologists in decision-making. Lighthouse labs were initially staffed by hundreds of research scientists and PhD students, subsequently replaced with recent science graduates, generally with no clinical laboratory experience. Testing services were made possible with this workforce through a very high division of labour to simplify testing processes at scale. Each of the Lighthouse Labs had an assigned consultant clinical virologist with NHS experience who was involved in the setup and oversight of the lab. However, as these clinical virologist advisors of Lighthouse Labs explained at interview, their remit was limited to their specific competency in conducting laboratory testing, rather than overall management of the lab. This is an important difference from traditional practice in NHS labs, where virologists have more management responsibilities, as two clinical virologists, who were advisors of Lighthouse Labs, explained:

“Each one of the [Lighthouse] laboratories appointed an [independent] experienced clinical virologist [...] responsible for the clinical aspects of testing. This is slightly different to a normal [...] NHS or PHE laboratory [where] the head of the laboratory would be a clinical scientist [or a] medically qualified clinical virologist [...] It is a different setup to what happens in the NHS.” (Lighthouse Lab advisor 2)

“The advisory role that I had and others had, was really to the labs, it was almost more of a quality [assurance] role, as in: ‘these are the kind of things you will need to do to run your lab properly.’ It wasn’t a day-to-day running of the lab [...] it was missing that.” (Lighthouse Lab advisor 4)

In summary, boundary work in line with the logic of efficiency predominated over the specialists’ professional criteria, resulting in a reduced role for clinical virologists in decision-making regarding the building and operation of the Lighthouse Labs, where the majority of the UK’s Covid-19 testing took place.

Boundary work and formal authority

The centralized control over Covid-19 testing in the UK, as well as the undermining of the medical profession’s control over the sociotechnical system for testing, are notable factors in

the UK case. Central government policymakers in London avoided tasking community testing to the PHE or NHS pathology labs, as these were seen to be overstretched or unable to scale-up fast enough. The chosen alternative option was to establish a new laboratory testing system outside of NHS hospitals or PHE, with this choice shaped more by non-specialists with a focus on efficiency rather than by the concerns of professional specialists.

Regardless of the lack of consultation with clinical virologists in system design, the benefits of from centralization were acknowledged by clinical virologists at interview, as illustrated by the following quote:

“Yeah, I guess the government from their point of view thought that [for] massive testing, obviously, it makes sense to centralize some of that activity, obviously, and that would make it easier in terms of the logistics.” (Clinical Virologist 1)

These benefits were argued to justify the establishment of the Lighthouse Labs as a UK-wide system, whereas healthcare provision is usually managed by devolved administrations. In contrast to the situation in Spain, where the Ministry of Health did not have the capacity to intervene in this way, the UK government’s willingness to fund these labs at a cost of tens of billions of pounds (as detailed in the contract for labs across the UK - see DHSC, 2020b), also furthered the adoption of this model by the much smaller devolved nations as one senior lab head recalled:

“DHSC were paying for it, you know, we [nation name] didn't have to pay for it [...] I think it turned out that DHSC paid for most of the testing throughout the pandemic, you know, in all the devolved [administrations] as well.” (Clinical Virologist 3)

The DHSC also had potent formal authority in terms of its financial power over NHS labs in England, which faced the threat of not being reimbursed if they increased their testing capacity beyond agreed levels, while also being expected to follow testing policy set by PHE, which NHS staff were not always comfortable with.

Apart from power over funding, the UK Government’s centralized decision makers also were able to call on the army to help develop their vision for the testing system. The army were used (amongst other things) to requisition PCR equipment from universities, hospitals, and research institutes to support the Lighthouse Lab network in set up and logistics.

In frustration, some labs “went a little bit rogue” (Clinical Virologist 1). When denied access by PHE to the positive control samples needed to establish in-house test assays, they obtained

these from European colleagues instead. When the army came to collect their PCR machines to establish the Lighthouse Laboratories, in some cases the troops were sent away with the older models rather than the best machines. When NHS England ordered that NHS staff should not be tested for Covid-19 to save limited test capacity for patients, pathology lab staff collaborated with local research labs to generate the required capacity to test NHS staff. Despite these acts of resistance, the majority of Covid-19 testing in the UK was ultimately undertaken by the new Lighthouse Labs (as shown in Figure 3).

Impact of boundary work after the pandemic acute phase

In early 2022, the government began a transition to ‘living with Covid-19’ (UK Cabinet Office, 2022), and opted not to renew the contracts of many Lighthouse Labs, with most ceasing operations by May 2022 (See Table 3 and Figure 3). A year later in 2023, the final labs in the network ceased operation (UKHSA, 2023a) with April 2023’s Covid-19 testing strategy completely excluding provision of PCR testing (UKHSA, 2023b).

Part of the initial rationale for the creation of the Lighthouse Lab network, was to support the UK’s future diagnostic capabilities, through the creation of high-throughput testing facilities – the DHSC testing strategy’s so-called ‘Pillar 5’ (DHSC, 2020b). However, the utility of high-throughput labs for purposes beyond Covid-19 was unclear, and the lack of flexibility in the functioning of the Lighthouse labs made them vulnerable to dismantling as some interviewees anticipated:

“The Lighthouse Labs are not flexible, they will disappear, all these new labs.” (Lighthouse Lab advisor 1)

“We didn’t need the capability we had then, so what makes you think there’s a purpose of these labs post-pandemic, and the answer is there is none, so they have to go. That is politically and practically, that is the right answer, we didn’t need them, we don’t need them, and now the pandemic is gone we don’t want them.” (Policymaker 5)

“I don’t know what the future of the [lab name] is [...] We’re a solution, essentially looking for a problem [...] Could we do monkeypox? Could we do blood transfusion? We’re still going to have to make significant changes to bring on new business [...] At the moment, we only deal with swabs, we’ve never dealt with blood [...]” (Lighthouse Lab Scientist 1)

The lack of flexibility in the Lighthouse labs utility reflects the initial design focus on simple, highly scalable Covid-19 testing. Subsequently the linkage to existing health systems and

practice was limited, and anticipated benefits for either industrial providers or the NHS's pathology services have not been realized.

Considering the large cost of the Lighthouse Lab network, a Parliamentary oversight committee's report on government spending criticized the DHSC for not articulating '*a legacy for the NHS through the vast investment in testing capacity*' which amounted to a budgeted £37 billion over two years (N.B. this figure includes costs of contact tracing and other testing technologies also used, such as antibody and antigen testing). The committee also questioned '*whether large testing centres were the best way forward in terms of an NHS legacy compared with having more capacity in local hospitals.*' (Public Accounts Committee, 2021; pp 7, 17). This concern regarding capacity has been echoed by clinical virologists writing in the British Medical Journal who note that 'Maintaining surplus laboratory capacity for emergencies is expensive, and therefore politically and economically unpalatable. Nevertheless, Covid-19 has shown that effective surge capacity is a vital part of pandemic preparedness.' (Skittrall et al, 2022).

The importance of a well-trained workforce of suitable size was emphasised by interviewees when asked about future pandemic planning:

"I think the pandemic highlighted the need for those staff, particularly the clinical scientists, to develop and implement tests and the biomedical scientists to run them. And I worry that has not been recognized [...] so we're going to end up with not that many virologists [and] clinical scientists." (Lighthouse Lab advisor 4)

"It's maintaining the experienced staff that gives you the ability to respond to a new pandemic [...] laboratories are built not upon the machines within them, but on the people that run them. And you lose that experience, [you have] nothing left." (Lighthouse advisor 2)

In summary, UK policy makers' long-term prioritization of efficiency, over the concerns of clinical professionals' drove the boundary work that shaped the organizational structure of the PCR testing for detection of Covid-19 in the community. Although a great volume of funding was made available to create and run Lighthouse Laboratories, the capabilities procured were largely outside of the NHS pathology services and have now been decommissioned, raising questions about future pandemic preparedness.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Our results show that boundary work in line with the professional logic can shape the organization of the healthcare system in a healthcare crisis if medical professionals have access to formal authority through prior institutional conditions. Yet we also show that if this is not the case, boundary work by non-specialists with access to formal authority may result in a focus on other priorities, such as efficiency. Findings illustrate how specific issues related to Covid-19 testing were resolved in these different ways in our two cases according to the centralization of formal authority in the UK versus regionally devolved authority in Spain. In the regions studied in Spain, the professional influence of those microbiologists with proximity to regional authorities seems to have ensured that public hospital labs retained responsibility for virtually all testing and analysis, largely excluding newly accredited external labs from the PCR testing system. Meanwhile in the UK, the influence of a small group of senior advisors, engaged in boundary work in line with the logic of efficiency, oversaw the establishment of Lighthouse Labs as a new organizational form, outside of the pre-pandemic clinical testing infrastructure. Moreover, relevant medical specialists, who would usually have professional responsibility for clinical testing services for infection, held only a limited role in the new organizational structure – which was largely created in their absence. We argue that rapid implementation of the non-specialist advisors’ radical vision, across the whole of the UK, was made possible due their proximity to centralized formal authority.

We thus show how radical organizational change in a crisis can be brought about in the context of established healthcare systems, even with limited involvement of key professionals – a finding that might be unexpected in Western healthcare systems. For example, Michael Mina, an epidemiologist at Harvard University, prominent in debates around the use of diagnostic tests for Covid-19, has characterized Western European countries and the United States as a "medical-centric group of countries" where "We have physicians running the show - that's a consistent thing" (Wallace-Wells, 2021). Yet the case of the Lighthouse Lab network appears to differ from the norms that Mina refers to. Here, boundary work in line with the logic of efficiency and the centralization of decision-making seem to have allowed the formation and running of Lighthouse Labs undertake ‘Pillar 2’ community testing in the UK for Covid-19. The UK case may be unusual, yet it reveals a limitation to the influence of boundary work in line with the professional logic, and highlights how the “physicians running the show” rely on institutional conditions modulating the territorial distribution of formal authority.

We also show how boundary work in line with the professional logic or the logic of efficiency may both be influential at the regional or national level of healthcare sociotechnical systems. This goes beyond the focus of the extant literature on boundary work within hospitals, e.g. around competition for new imaging technologies within or between different hospital services (Lindberg et al., 2017; Barrett et al., 2012; Burri, 2008, Blume, 1992; Barley, 1986). Our work also builds on the organizational literature that has probed the intersection between boundary work and institutions (Zietsma and Lawrence, 2010; Langley et al., 2019; Mikes, 2011). Our article contributes to this literature by approaching the interplay between boundary work inspired by institutional logics and other types of institutions regulating the territorial distribution of formal authority, thus following the call of Langley et al.'s (2019) review on boundary work that urged researchers to inquire into the role of formal authority. The context of the Covid-19 pandemic has allowed us to verify that these various institutional influences, based on existing conditions pre-dating the crisis, have been fundamental in the organization and impact of the response to the epidemic.

A limitation of this research is that the authors only had opportunity to study the focal institutional context during the pandemic and not before the onset of the crisis. Had this not been the case, more details on the prevailing institutional conditions might have been gathered. Future work might explore whether the findings reported here are echoed in other aspects of the Covid-19 response in the UK and Spain (e.g. around vaccination, contact tracing, testing for travel) or other countries where the dynamics observed here could offer the opportunity to confirm or extend the conceptual contributions we put forward.

It is beyond the scope of this article to make a technical judgment about the performance of these different designs of testing systems (e.g. their relative cost effectiveness or safety). However, what does seem apparent is that, after the acute phase of the crisis, the legacy of the pandemic response has been very different in these two countries. In Spain, the resources allocated to public hospital labs to expand their PCR capacity has seemingly extended and improved their diagnostic capabilities and pandemic preparedness. Yet in the UK, concerns have been raised that the Lighthouse Labs leave little tangible infrastructural legacy, despite vast funding being expended on them (Public Accounts Committee, 2021). A former chief scientific adviser to the government stated in April 2023 that “we’re in the same position as we were in 2020. Nothing has changed... if anything it has got worse.” (Thomas and Kingsley, 2023). We suggest that the new capacity and expertise created during the Covid-19 response

was largely kept outside the UK's pre-existing clinical virology labs, due to boundary work in line with the logic of efficiency by those outside this professional community.

It remains to be seen what the impact of the two distinct organizational arrangements described here may be on any future pandemic responses, however our findings provide an opportunity to reflect on the importance of pre-existing institutional conditions when considering the composition of decision making bodies that will operate during a healthcare crisis. The policy implication here is that because prior institutional conditions are influential in shaping the response during a crisis, it is all the more important for stakeholders to question these arrangements in preparation for a possible future crisis.

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ANNEX 1. ESTIMATING “EXTERNAL” TESTING VOLUMES IN SPAIN

We knew from our interviews that many of the accredited laboratories did not start operations related with PCR testing, but we needed to undertake further research to reach an estimation of the number of external labs actively providing PCR testing.

We searched for online news (see sources in Table A.1) about laboratories contributing with their PCR capacity and found reports on 11 laboratories. Additionally, we emailed a sample of these and 24 others from the list of 85 approved by ISCIII. We selected the sample from the laboratories that most directly identified the microbiology laboratory manager on their websites. We had a total of 19 responses, with 2 laboratories reporting PCR testing activity that we did not find in our initial online news search. Extrapolating from these results to the total

population of 85 ISCIII accredited laboratories, our estimation is that about 20 external laboratories were active during the Covid-19 pandemic.

We were able to collect data from about total tests reported, period of activity, demonstrated peak capacity and target population for 5 labs (see Table A.2). An estimation using the average total number of tests of the external labs suggests about 400,000 PCR tests performed by the external labs during the pandemic, which is just 0.7 % of the national total. Although our estimation is admittedly rough, it can give an indication of the modest contribution of the external laboratory network in Spain, as the rest of the PCR testing was undertaken in clinical labs.

[INSERT TABLE A.1 AND TABLE A.2 ABOUT HERE]